

Methods of teaching students the rules of correct writing

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada, to'g'ri yozishga o'rgatish uslublari: namunaga qarab yozish, ko'chirib yozish, genetik usul kabi bir qancha to'g'ri yozishga o'rgatish qoidalari haqida yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Harf, sanoq-ohang usuli, genetik usul, chiroyli yozuv.

Аннотация: В этой статье обсуждаются несколько методов обучения правильному письму, такие как образцовое письмо, копирайтинг и генетический метод

Ключевые слова: Письмо, цифро-тоновый метод, генетический метод, красивое письмо.

Abstract: In this article, several methods of teaching correct writing, such as model writing, copy writing, and genetic method, are discussed

Key words: Letter, number-tone method, genetic method, beautiful writing.

Writing teaching methods:

1. Pattern writing

One of the most important ways to teach good writing is to model and write the shape of the letters. The teacher should show a sample of each letter on the board, drawing the attention of all students, or writing it down (with a red pen) in the student's notebook. The task of the student is to correctly reflect the memorized

forms (letters, syllables, words) in their notebooks.

Each letter written on the board should be clearly visible to all students, if some students could not see it, it should be shown again. It is especially important to show a new letter or their combination, repeating it over and over again in time.

The connection of each letter or letters by the teacher, by explaining orally or on the board, where the hand should be placed, where the movement of the hand needs to be turned and where this movement needs to be stopped, how high and low the letters, etc. are explained in the instructions.

Later, the students explain the spelling of a particular letter as the teacher explained.

2. Copy and write according to the sample

In the method of copying and writing according to the model, students copy and write down the form of the harp according to the model in the book "Khusnihat" or "Yazuv Daftari".

Copying and pattern writing is more difficult than writing over ready-made letters, and the teacher must know well when to use both.

The exercise by moving the hand over the letters represented by the dots is an involuntary process, and students can easily cope with this task. For example, the capital letter O is practiced as follows:

Each example written by the teacher in the students' notebooks should be written beautifully and clearly.

Writing according to the example given in the Husnihat textbook saves the teacher's time and creates an opportunity for productive work. For this, every student should have a textbook.

3. (genetic) method for analyzing the shape of letters.

It is a method of studying the analysis of writing and its (elemental) elements, which can be implemented in different ways.

Students are taught to analyze letters by dividing them into elements, how many elements each letter consists of, what shape each element has, and how these elements look when combined with other letters. But the alphabet of simplified letters recommends writing many letters as a whole, without dividing them into elements. For example, lowercase letters b and f are written as a whole, without being divided into elements.

Some letters consist of several elements that are written as a whole, but the teacher can only recall how many elements it consists of. For example, the first element of the lowercase letters n and m has the same shape, but the lowercase n has one small stick with a loop, and the lowercase m has two curved sticks.

Here only the teacher mentions how many elements the letters consist of, and when writing these letters, it is necessary to write them without stopping the movement of the hand.

4. Tone method

When using the count-tone method, the teacher explains the letter and its elements by counting them. This method can be widely used, especially during the period of literacy.

The advantage of the digital tone method is that, firstly, it ensures that letters are written evenly and does not allow letter elements to fall out; secondly, it encourages students who write slowly to write quickly and on an equal footing with all students in the class; thirdly, it teaches students to perform actions clearly

and boldly; Fourth, it helps bring the lesson to life in the classroom.

But it is not recommended to use this method throughout the lesson, as students may get tired and reduce the quality of writing.

When using the digital-tone method, the main element of the letters is considered as "one", "two", "three", and the auxiliary connecting element is connected as "and".

For example, writing a lowercase m can be practiced as follows.

When using the digital tone method, letters or elements are first written without a number, and then with a number.

Also, when writing with this method, it is shown that at first it is written slowly, and then faster.

The number tone method can also be used to write syllables, words, and sentences.

5. A way of writing letters at the same height.

Starting from the 3rd quarter of the 2nd grade, students begin to write in a one-line notebook. During this period, it is necessary to write letters at the same height (small letters 3 mm, capital letters 6-7 mm). A student who previously learned to write in a notebook in two lines, writes with difficulty in a large notebook, and his handwriting begins to deteriorate. During this period, it is necessary to write letters at the same height, that is, the height of lowercase letters is 3 mm, and the height of uppercase letters is 6 mm.

Summary

In conclusion, writing skills are more complex than reading skills. Therefore, the period of learning the alphabet, allotted for training sessions in the

first grade, can be somewhat extended (in the book "Alfibe" 20-25 days are allotted for this period). But during this period there may be some difference between the writing lesson and the reading lesson, this should not be alarming, since at this time the students learn to write words and letters based on the material they have studied.

Later, reading and writing lessons continue to be inextricably linked. Preparatory exercises are given taking into account some aspects that are relevant for writing classes.

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